

Graphical Abstract

Forced Periodic Operation of Chemical Reactors: Origins of Performance Improvement Demonstrated for Methanol Synthesis

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Highlights

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- Forced periodic operation (FPO) is beneficial for simultaneous flow rate and composition modulations with phase shift
- FPO is beneficial due to the residence time effect, which originates from the bilinear nature of the reactor equation
- The further the reactor operates away from chemical equilibrium, the greater the potential for improvement through FPO.
- A fixed-bed reactor offers a higher potential for improvement under FPO compared to a CSTR.
- Findings are demonstrated for methanol synthesis as an industrial relevant case study.

Forced Periodic Operation of Chemical Reactors: Origins of Performance Improvement Demonstrated for Methanol Synthesis

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Abstract

It has been shown that simultaneous periodic forcing of feed flow rate and feed composition, with a phase shift, can significantly improve the performance of chemical reactors. This work investigates the fundamental origins of the performance improvements under this type of forced periodic operation (FPO). Using a simple $A \rightarrow C$ reaction as a model system, it is demonstrated that improvements can occur even for linear kinetics due to the bilinear nature of the reactor equations. This bilinearity arises when the inlet molar flow rate is treated as a perturbed input variable. The additional simultaneous modulation of the inlet concentration with a phase shift leads to a physical residence time effect that brings the mean composition closer to chemical equilibrium and enables transitions between batch and continuous operation. Subsequent analysis of methanol synthesis confirms that the same mechanism applies to complex reaction networks and real-world reactor systems. The results show that the improvement potential depends on the distance from chemical equilibrium and that tubular reactors exhibit higher improvement potential than continuous stirred-tank reactors. These findings establish that FPO is not limited to special reaction systems with specific nonlinear kinetics but may be beneficial for a wide range of chemical processes.

Keywords: Forced periodic operation, Chemical reactors, Multi-objective optimization, Methanol synthesis, Bilinear reactor equation

1. Introduction

Forced periodic operation (FPO) is based on the idea of periodically perturbing reactor inputs to achieve, on average, a higher product yield or conversion than under comparable steady state operation. The concept dates back to the pioneering work of Horn and Baily [1] and has since been applied to a variety of chemical systems. A comprehensive overview of the development and applications of FPO can be found in the review by Silveston [2]. A fundamental requirement for achieving improvement through FPO compared to steady state operation is the presence of nonlinearity in the system behavior [3]. To translate this potential into actual performance gains, it is crucial to identify which input variables can be effectively modulated and how many are needed. In recent years, the nonlinear frequency response (NFR) method has provided significant insights into this topic, particularly in the context of chemical reactors[4, 3, 5] . Using this approach, it was demonstrated for a single-input periodic modulation that the reaction order must be different from one in order to achieve improvement, which means that the reaction rate must be at least nonlinear [3]. Furthermore, it has been shown that the simultaneous periodic modulation of two inputs, with a phase shift offers greater potential for improvement, i.e., the combined modulation of the inlet flow rate and inlet concentration with a defined phase difference. In this case, improvements can even be achieved even for reactions with reaction order one [6].

According to these studies, only mathematical explanations are provided why this improvements are possible, attributing any improvement through FPO solely to system nonlinearities. It is generally stated that identifying a simple physical reason for the observed improvement is difficult [7]. Therefore, most investigations focus on whether improvement is possible rather than on understanding why it occurs [7, 8, 9, 10]. In the experimental validation of the NFR method for the reaction of acetic anhydride by Felischak et al., a proposed physical explanation for the observed improvement was that phases of low flow rate coincide with high reactant concentration, and vice versa, highlighting the critical role of the residence time [11].

The present work builds upon this idea of residence time as a key factor and aims to address the current lack of a simple and clear physical explanation for the performance improvements observed in chemical reactors under FPO with simultaneous modulation of two inputs and a phase shift. For this purpose, the first part of this study analyzes a simple homogeneous reaction,

38 $A \rightarrow C$. The best possible steady state and best possible FPO conditions are
 39 compared to reveal the full improvement potential. It is shown that improve-
 40 ments can occur through FPO even though the reaction rate is linear, due to
 41 the bilinear nature of the reactor equations themselves, when the inlet flow
 42 rate is treated as a perturbed input. The underlying physical reason for this
 43 behavior is investigated in detail, showing that the improvement originates
 44 from the residence time effect, which is explained later in this work. In the
 45 second part, a case study for methanol synthesis, which has recently been
 46 studied in the context of FPO [8, 9, 12, 13], illustrates that the residence
 47 time effect alone can largely explain the observed performance benefits for
 48 an real-world process.

49 **2. Theoretical Basis: FPO Applied to a Linear Reaction Model**

50 To isolate the basic effect of forced periodic operation in chemical reactors
 51 a simple reaction

52 is considered, where A is the reactant and C the product. The reaction is
 53 assumed to follow a first-order power-law rate expression, given by

$$r = k \cdot V \cdot c_A = k \cdot n \cdot y_A \quad (2)$$

54 where r is the reaction rate, k is the rate constant, n is the total mole number,
 55 and y_A is the molar fraction of component A . To realize the FPO, the inlet
 56 molar flow rate, \dot{n}_{in} , and the inlet concentration are periodically perturbed
 57 simultaneously with phase shift, as this combination has proven to be the
 58 most promising [6, 5]. The periodic excitation is defined as follows:

$$y_{A,\text{in}}(t) = y_{A,\text{in},0} [1 + A_A \text{squ}(\omega t)], \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) = \dot{n}_{\text{in},0} [1 + A_n \text{squ}(\omega t + \varphi)], \quad (4)$$

59 where A_A and A_n are the relative amplitudes of the inlet concentration and
 60 molar flow rate oscillations, ω is the frequency, and φ is the phase shift
 61 between both signals. It is well known that square-wave forcing generally
 62 results in a higher improvement than harmonic excitation [8, 14]. However,
 63 to maintain differentiability of the perturbation, a smooth square-wave ap-
 64 proximation is employed by combining a hyperbolic tangent with a cosine

Figure 1: Periodic input function evaluated over the interval $-2\pi \leq \omega t \leq 2\pi$.

65 function, defined as:

$$\text{squ}(\omega t) = \tanh(-10 \cos(\omega t)). \quad (5)$$

66 Figure 1 shows the function over the interval from -2π to 2π . To make the
 67 inlet concentration perturbation feasible while keeping the total concentra-
 68 tion constant, the reactor feed also contains an inert component B e. g.
 69 solvent, which compensates for the modulation of the inlet concentration of
 70 A :

$$y_{B,\text{in}}(t) = y_{B,\text{in},0} [1 - A_B \text{squ}(\omega t)]. \quad (6)$$

71 The equality constraint

$$A_A \cdot y_{A,\text{in},0} + A_B \cdot y_{B,\text{in},0} = 0, \quad (7)$$

72 ensures that the summation condition for the inlet mole fractions,

$$y_{A,\text{in}}(t) + y_{B,\text{in}}(t) = 1, \quad (8)$$

73 is satisfied at all times. It is assumed that in steady state 50% A and 50%
 74 B as inert are present at the inlet. As the objective function, the average
 75 flow rate of component C at the outlet

$$\Phi_1 = \overline{\dot{n}_{C,\text{out}}} = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{out}}(t) \cdot y_{C,\text{out}}(t) dt \quad (9)$$

$$(10)$$

76 and the average yield of C related to A at the inlet is considered

$$\Phi_2 = \bar{Y} = \frac{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{out}(t) \cdot y_{C,out}(t)}{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{in}(t) \cdot y_{A,in}(t)} \quad (11)$$

$$(12)$$

77 In the following, the reaction is analyzed in a continuous stirred tank reactor
 78 (CSTR) and in a plug flow tubular reactor (PFTR) to compare their behavior
 79 under FPO.

80 2.1. Continuous stirred tank reactor

81 First, it is assumed that the reaction takes place in a CSTR. Since the
 82 total number of moles remains constant during the reaction, the inlet and
 83 outlet molar flow rates are equal. The corresponding partial molar balances
 84 are given by:

$$n \frac{dy_A}{dt} = \dot{n}_{in}(t) [y_{A,in}(t) - y_A] - k n y_A, \quad (13)$$

$$n \frac{dy_B}{dt} = \dot{n}_{in}(t) [y_{B,in}(t) - y_B], \quad (14)$$

$$n \frac{dy_C}{dt} = -\dot{n}_{in}(t) y_C + k n y_A. \quad (15)$$

85 In order to obtain a periodic solution, a periodicity condition is introduced
 86 as

$$y_i(0) = y_i(\tau), \quad (16)$$

87 where $\tau = \frac{2\pi}{\omega}$ denotes the period of the forced oscillation. To reveal the full
 88 potential of FPO with simultaneous modulation of flow rate and composition
 89 with phase shift, it is essential to compare the best possible steady state
 90 operation with the best possible periodic operation. For the steady state
 91 case, assuming a constant average inlet flow rate of $\dot{n}_{in,0} = 1$ mol/s and a
 92 total mole number of $n = 1$ mol, the degree of freedom for optimization is
 93 zero, and the solution is unique.

94 In periodic operation, the amplitudes, the period length $\tau = 2\pi/\omega$, and
 95 the phase shift are optimized. It is further ensured that the same total
 96 amount of inert as in steady state operation is present in the reactor to allow
 97 for a fair comparison:

$$\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{in}^{FPO}(t) y_{B,in}^{FPO}(t) dt = \dot{n}_{in}^{SS} y_{B,in}^{SS}. \quad (17)$$

Table 1: Summary of fixed and optimized parameters as well as objective functions for steady state and FPO in CSTR.

Parameters		SS	FPO	Unit
Fixed	k	1	1	1/s
	n	1	1	mol
	$\dot{n}_{\text{in},0}$	1	1	mol/s
Optimized	$y_{A,\text{in},0}$ [0, 1]	0.5	0.5	–
	$y_{B,\text{in},0}$ [0, 1]	0.5	0.5	–
	A_A [0, 1]	0	1	–
	A_B [0, 1]	0	1	–
	A_n [0, 1]	0	1	–
	φ [0, 2π]	–	0.5π	rad
	τ [0.36, 360]	–	1.7899	s
Objectives	Φ_1	0.25	0.2791 (+11.64%)	mol/s
	Φ_2	0.50	0.5582 (+11.64%)	–

104 This also implies that the factors preceding the periodic excitation, $y_{A,\text{in},0}$
105 and $y_{B,\text{in},0}$, represent additional degrees of freedom. Since the average inlet
106 composition under periodic operation is equal to that of the steady state
107 case, the two objective functions, Φ_1 and Φ_2 , are not independent. Therefore,
108 optimizing one of them is sufficient. The optimization problem is formulated
109 as follows:

$$\max_{\mathbf{u}} \Phi_1 \quad (18)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = f(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}), \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}(\tau), \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (21)$$

104 where \mathbf{x} denotes the state vector and \mathbf{u} the vector of manipulated inputs. The
105 optimization problem is solved simultaneously by discretizing the system of
106 ordinary differential equations using finite differences with 300 discretization
107 points [15, 16].

108 The optimal parameters and corresponding objective functions are sum-
109 marized in Table 1. With these optimal parameters, an improvement of
110 11.64% in both yield and outlet flow rate is achieved under FPO. The tem-
111 poral evolution of the product flow rate as well as the inlet trajectories over

Figure 2: Temporal profiles of inlet and outlet variables for the reaction $A \rightarrow B$ in CSTR under forced periodic operation.

112 one period are shown in Figure 2. The figure also illustrates the inlet mole
 113 fractions, the overall inlet molar flow rate, and the individual inlet molar
 114 flow rates of components A and B, providing a better understanding of the
 115 process dynamics. The optimized phase shift leads to an operation consisting
 116 of three distinct phases. In the first phase, the reactor is charged with the
 117 reactant, where only component A enters. In the second phase, the total inlet
 118 flow rate becomes zero resulting in a batch-like operation without any inflow
 119 or outflow. During this phase, the system approaches chemical equilibrium

120 much closer than under steady state conditions. The final phase corresponds
 121 to the discharge of the product, during which the reactor is flushed with the
 122 inert component B . This represents the optimal FPO case in the absence
 123 of any additional nonlinear effects from the reaction. For more complex re-
 124 action networks, the optimal input trajectories also become more intricate
 125 and physically harder to interpret. Nevertheless, the underlying principle is
 126 evident: the improvement arises from a temporary increase of the residence
 127 time, approaching batch operation when a high amount of reactant is present
 128 in the reactor, followed by a rapid discharge. In the following, this effect is
 129 referred to as the "residence time effect".

130 Now the question arises why an improvement can be observed, although
 131 a linear reaction system has been considered. In principle, a system must be
 132 nonlinear in order to exhibit any improvement under periodic operation. For
 133 a linear system, periodic excitation of the inputs u results, on average, in the
 134 same outcome as in steady state operation [3]. For better understanding, the
 135 system can be expressed in matrix–vector form as

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} y_A \\ y_B \\ y_C \end{bmatrix}, \quad u = \begin{bmatrix} y_{A,\text{in}} \\ y_{B,\text{in}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

136 The corresponding dynamic equations are then given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) + k n}{n} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t)}{n} & 0 \\ k & 0 & -\frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t)}{n} \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t)}{n} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t)}{n} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} u(t). \quad (22)$$

137 If \dot{n}_{in} is considered as an input, a product term of $u \cdot x$ appears in the
 138 system equations. This makes the system bilinear. Therefore, forced periodic
 139 operation could theoretically be beneficial not only because of nonlinearities
 140 in the reaction kinetics, but also due to the bilinear nature of the reactor
 141 equations themselves. For an isothermal CSTR, this implies not only that
 142 the simultaneous modulation of at least two inputs with a phase shift is most
 143 promising, but also that one of these modulated inputs must be the flow rate

144 in order to achieve performance improvements independently of the reaction
145 kinetics.

146 As the inlet flow rate, and thus the residence time, cause the improvement
147 of reactor performance in FPO, the following part investigates their effect on
148 the potential for improvement.

149 *Influence of inlet flow rate*

150 The yield and the product flow rate represent conflicting objectives. To
151 increase the yield, the inlet flow rate can be reduced, which, however, si-
152 multaneously decreases the product flow rate and vice versa. With forced
153 periodic operation, both objectives can be improved at the same time. To
154 illustrate this, a multi-objective optimization is performed, and the Pareto
155 front is computed by using the inlet flow rate as additional decision vari-
156 able. The bounds for the inlet flowrate are set to 0.2 mol/s and 5 mol/s. The
157 multiobjective optimization problem is solved using the ε -constraint method
158 [17]:

$$\min_{\mathbf{u}} \Phi_1 \quad (23)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = f(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}), \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}(\tau), \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (26)$$

$$\Phi_2 = \varepsilon. \quad (27)$$

159 By systematically varying ε , different Pareto-optimal solutions are obtained,
160 representing the trade-off between Φ_1 and Φ_2 . Both the optimal steady state
161 and the optimal periodic Pareto fronts are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen
162 that the Pareto front of the periodic operation lies above that of the steady
163 state, indicating an improvement through FPO under all operating points.
164 In addition to the Pareto fronts themselves, the optimal inlet flow rates and
165 corresponding period lengths along the fronts are also shown. As expected,
166 higher inlet flow rates result in higher product flow rates but lower yields, and
167 vice versa. In the Pareto front of the FPO optimization, the improvement
168 compared to steady state operation becomes more pronounced at higher inlet
169 flow rates, i.e., at lower residence times, when the reactor operates further
170 away from chemical equilibrium. This leads to the general conclusion that
171 the further the reactor operates from chemical equilibrium, the greater the
172 potential of improvement through FPO.

Figure 3: Comparison of steady state and FPO Pareto fronts for the reaction $A \rightarrow B$ in the CSTR with variable inlet flow rate \dot{n}_{in} .

173 *2.2. Plug Flow Tubular Reactor*

174 In the next step, the same analysis is performed for a PFTR. The corre-
 175 sponding reactor equations, derived from the component mass balances, are
 176 given by:

$$n \frac{\partial y_A}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_A}{\partial z} = -k n y_A, \quad (28)$$

$$n \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (29)$$

$$n \frac{\partial y_C}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_C}{\partial z} = k n y_A, \quad (30)$$

177 subject to the boundary and periodicity conditions:

$$y_i(t, 0) = y_{i,\text{in}}(t), \quad (31)$$

$$y_i(0, z) = y_i(\tau, z). \quad (32)$$

Table 2: Summary of fixed and optimized parameters as well as objective functions for steady state and FPO in PFTR.

Parameters		SS	FPO	Unit
Fixed	k	$\ln(2)$	$\ln(2)$	mol/s
	n	1	1	mol
	$\dot{n}_{\text{in},0}$	1	1	mol/s
	l	1	1	m
Optimized	$y_{A,\text{in},0}$ [0, 1]	0.5	0.5	–
	$y_{B,\text{in},0}$ [0, 1]	0.5	0.5	–
	A_A [0, 1]	0	1	–
	A_B [0, 1]	0	1	–
	A_n [0, 1]	0	1	–
	φ [0, 2π]	–	0.5π	rad
	τ [0.36, 360]	–	2.2504	s
Objectives	Φ_1	0.25	0.3102 (+24.06%)	mol/s
	Φ_2	0.50	0.6204 (+24.06%)	–

178 The reactor length is set to $l = 1$ m. A Detailed explanation of the reactor
179 equations can be found in the Supporting Information. For the present ex-
180 ample plug flow reactors exhibit higher efficiency than CSTRs for the same
181 reactor size. To ensure a fair comparison between the two reactor types, the
182 steady state objective values for CSTR and PFTR should be identical. To
183 achieve this, the reactor equations of the PFTR can be solved analytically
184 in steady state. By fixing the product flow rate at 0.25 mol s^{-1} , the reaction
185 rate constant can be determined and set to $k = \ln(2) 1/\text{s}$. Also in this case,
186 the optimal steady state operation is compared with the optimal forced peri-
187 odic operation. The results are summarized in Table 2. An improvement of
188 24.06 % through FPO compared to steady state operation is obtained. This
189 improvement is approximately twice as large as that achieved for the CSTR.
190 The optimal parameters are identical to those of the CSTR case, except for
191 the period, which is 2.2 s. To provide further insight into the reason for the
192 greater improvement, the dynamic profiles at the reactor inlet and outlet
193 over time are shown in Figure 4. Due to the identical optimal parameters,
194 the inlet trajectories appear similar to those of the CSTR, showing the same
195 three phases of charging, batch, and discharging. The main difference is
196 observed in the outlet molar flow rates during the charging phase. In the
197 CSTR, the ideally mixed behavior causes an increase in the outlet flow rate

Figure 4: Temporal profiles of inlet and outlet variables for the reaction $A \rightarrow B$ in PFTR under forced periodic operation.

198 of component A during the charging phase, which lowers the average yield
 199 since unreacted A leaves the reactor. In contrast, in the PFTR this effect is
 200 absent due to the spatial distribution and the resulting time delay between
 201 inlet and outlet caused by transportation. During the filling phase, mainly
 202 the inert component is displaced from the reactor, and only a minor amount
 203 of component A leaves the reactor, which results in a higher improvement
 204 compared to the CSTR. For better illustration, a video showing the temporal
 205 profiles along the reactor length is provided as Supporting Information.

206 Up to now, it has been theoretically demonstrated that improvements
 207 can be achieved in both the CSTR and the PFTR, independently of the
 208 nonlinearity of the reaction rate. From this analysis, three main conclusions

209 can be drawn:

- 210 • FPO is beneficial due to the "residence time effect", which originates
211 from the bilinear nature of the system when the inlet flow rate is chosen
212 as the perturbed input.
- 213 • The further the reactor operates away from chemical equilibrium, the
214 greater the potential for improvement through FPO.
- 215 • The PFTR offers a higher potential for improvement under FPO than
216 the CSTR.

217 To demonstrate these theoretical findings for a realistic industrial process, a
218 case study for methanol synthesis is presented in the following.

219 **3. Case study: Methanol synthesis**

220 Methanol is an important platform chemical and energy carrier, serving as
221 a feedstock for numerous downstream products such as formaldehyde, acetic
222 acid, or dimethyl ether [18]. Industrial methanol synthesis is carried out
223 over a copper-based catalyst, typically in fixed-bed reactors (FBR), and in-
224 volves three main reactions: carbon monoxide hydrogenation, carbon dioxide
225 hydrogenation, and the reverse water–gas shift (RWGS) reaction:

226 In recent years, it has been shown that methanol synthesis is a suitable
227 candidate for achieving theoretical improvements through FPO. [7, 8, 9, 19]
228 Methanol synthesis is an exothermic process. However, it was demonstrated
229 that the Pareto fronts for the isothermal and non-isothermal cases are very
230 similar. The only significant differences were found in the optimal inlet and
231 cooling temperatures, which are lower in the non-isothermal case [9]. Since
232 the present work focuses on the fundamental reasons for the improvement
233 under FPO, and the isothermal and non-isothermal cases exhibit comparable
234 trends, only the isothermal reactor with constant temperature of $T = 503\text{K}$
235 is considered here in order to eliminate additional nonlinearities other than

236 the bilinearity and those originating from the reaction rate. Accordingly, the
 237 system can be described by the following partial molar balance equations:

$$n^G \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial t} + \dot{n} l \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial z} = m_{\text{cat}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{ij} r_j - y_i \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{ij} r_j \right). \quad (36)$$

238 Due to the mole-reducing nature of the reaction system, the overall molar
 239 balance must be considered:

$$l \frac{\partial \dot{n}}{\partial z} = m_{\text{cat}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j. \quad (37)$$

240 The kinetic model proposed by Seidel et al. [20, 21] with parameters from
 241 [22] was used, as it is fitted to dynamic data, making it particularly suitable
 242 for FPO. The accumulation in the solid phase is neglected in this work. It
 243 has been considered in several other studies. Its influence on FPO was shown
 244 by Seidel *et al.* [7] However, the actual extent of this accumulation remains
 245 uncertain and is difficult to determine experimentally. Therefore, it is not
 246 taken into account here. A detailed explanation of the molar balance and
 247 kinetics is provided in the Supporting Information. First, the differences in
 248 performance of methanol synthesis under FPO between the CSTR and the
 249 FBR is investigated.

250 3.1. Comparison of CSTR and FBR

251 A fixed-bed reactor model based on the configuration used by Nestler et
 252 al. was adopted for the theoretical analysis in this study [23]. The corre-
 253 sponding reactor geometry and parameters are listed in Table 3. The result-
 254 ing partial differential equations were discretized using finite differences with
 255 50 points in the spatial domain and 50 points in time. To obtain a CSTR
 256 with comparable proportions, two discretization points were used in spatial
 257 domain, corresponding to the reactor inlet (z_1) and outlet (z_2).

258 The objective functions are defined similarly to the analysis presented
 259 before. On the one hand, the average product flow rate per catalyst mass is
 260 considered as

$$\Phi_1 = \frac{\overline{\dot{n}_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH},\text{out}}}}{m_{\text{cat}}} = \frac{1}{\tau m_{\text{cat}}} \int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{out}}(t) y_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH},\text{out}}(t) dt, \quad (38)$$

Table 3: Summary of reactor parameters for the original and adjusted fixed-bed reactor [23]

Parameter		Original Reactor	Adjusted Reactor	Unit
Reactor length:	l	1.12	1.12	m
Reactor inner diameter:	d_{int}	1.3	1.182	cm
Catalyst mass:	m_{cat}	168.85	139.495	g
Pressure:	p	60	60	bar
Temperature:	T	503.15	503.15	K
Average Feed flow rate:	$\dot{n}_{in,0}$	0.0221	0.0221	mol/s
total gas amount:	n^G	0.0831	0.0688	mol

261 and on the other hand, the average yield based on carbon in the feed is
 262 defined as

$$\Phi_2 = \bar{Y} = \frac{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{out}(t) y_{CH_3OH,out}(t) dt}{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{in}(t) (y_{CO_2,in}(t) + y_{CO,in}(t)) dt}. \quad (39)$$

263 As excitation variables, the simultaneous modulation of the CO inlet con-
 264 centration and the inlet molar flow rate with a phase shift is applied [13].
 265 This corresponds to the excitations defined in Eqs. (3), (4), and (6), where
 266 component A now represents CO and component B the inert corresponds to
 267 N₂. Figure 5 shows the resulting Pareto fronts for steady state and periodic
 268 operation. Both curves exhibit a similar qualitative shape, indicating that
 269 improvements are possible for both the CSTR and the FBR under FPO.
 270 The improvement is smaller at low yields and increases along the Pareto
 271 front with higher yields. To quantify the improvement, the methanol flow
 272 rate at the lowest point of the periodic front is selected and projected onto
 273 the steady state front as reference point. At this point, the CSTR shows an
 274 improvement of 45.2% in yield at the same flow rate and an improvement of
 275 366.4% in flow rate at the same yield under FPO. In contrast, the improve-
 276 ment for the FBR is lower than predicted in the section before. Here, a yield
 277 improvement of 32.2% at the same flow rate and a flow-rate improvement
 278 of 221.7% at the same yield are obtained. The reason for this behavior is
 279 that, in steady state operation, the FBR already achieves a higher maximum
 280 yield of 55% compared to 44% in the CSTR, as well as a higher flow rate
 281 (891 mmol/min/kg_{cat} compared to 830 mmol/min/kg_{cat}). In addition to the
 282 Pareto fronts, the equilibrium yields corresponding to the steady state com-
 283 positions are also included in the plots. Due to the higher yield in the FBR,

Figure 5: Comparison of CSTR and FBR performance under steady state and FPO conditions for methanol synthesis.

284 this reactor operates closer to chemical equilibrium, which, as shown in the
 285 section before, results in a lower potential for improvement.

286 Please note that the chemical equilibrium is shown only corresponding
 287 to the steady state case and depends on the inlet composition. Since the
 288 composition varies periodically under FPO, a different equilibrium exists
 289 at each point in time. However, including these values would make the
 290 plots overly complex and would not provide additional insight. A detailed
 291 explanation and illustration are provided in the Supporting Information.

292 Since the FBR provides a higher yield at the same reactor volume, the
 293 comparison is not entirely fair when evaluating the potential of improvement.
 294 To enable a fair comparison between the two reactor types, a case was identi-
 295 fied in which the CSTR and FBR achieve in steady state the same methanol
 296 flow rate at a yield of 40 %. For this purpose, the reactor diameter of the FBR
 297 was artificially reduced until this condition was met. The resulting reactor
 298 diameter and all relevant parameters are summarized in Table 3. Figure 6
 299 shows the Pareto fronts of the two comparable reactors. It can be observed
 300 that at the point $\Phi_1 = 677 \text{ mmol/min/kg}_{\text{cat}}$ and $\Phi_2 = 40 \%$, the steady state
 301 fronts of the CSTR and the smaller FBR coincide. This point is used as a ref-

Figure 6: Comparison of CSTR and adjusted FBR performance under steady state and FPO conditions for methanol synthesis.

302 erence in the following discussion. It is now evident that the Pareto front of
 303 the FPO operation in the FBR lies above that of the CSTR. For the CSTR,
 304 an improvement of 14.2% in yield at the same methanol flow rate and 16%
 305 in methanol flow rate at the same yield is achieved under FPO. In contrast,
 306 the FBR exhibits an improvement of 17.1% in yield and 23.1% in methanol
 307 flow rate. This confirms the previously proposed statement that, for steady
 308 state operation points with the same distance to chemical equilibrium, the
 309 FBR shows a higher potential for improvement under FPO compared to the
 310 CSTR.

311 Finally, the contribution of the "residence time effect" and the contribu-
 312 tions resulting from the nonlinearity of the reaction kinetics to the overall
 313 FPO improvement are analyzed.

314 3.2. Contribution of the residence time effect to the overall potential of im- 315 provement

316 For a linear reaction rate, it has been shown that the improvement re-
 317 sults solely from the bilinear nature of the reactor and the resulting physical
 318 "residence time effect". To quantify the relative contribution of this effect

Table 4: Reactor parameters for the isothermal CSTR from Vollbrecht [28]

Parameter		Value	Unit
Reactor Volume:	V	10.3	cm^3
Catalyst mass:	m_{cat}	3.95	g
Pressure:	p	50	bar
Temperature:	T	503.15	K
Average Feed flow rate:	$\dot{n}_{\text{in},0}$	0.1762	mmol/s
total gas amount:	n^G	0.0123	mol

319 in methanol synthesis, the Pareto front obtained with the nonlinear reaction
 320 kinetics is compared to that obtained using a linearized kinetic model.

321 The kinetic model proposed by Seidel *et al.* includes an additional nonlin-
 322 ear ordinary differential equations to describe the catalyst state [20, 21]. To
 323 avoid introducing further nonlinearities into the system, other kinetic models
 324 from the literature are therefore used instead: the Vanden Bussche kinetics,
 325 which represents one of the earliest developed models [24]; the Nestler kinet-
 326 ics, which is a refitted version of the Graaf model [25]; the Brilman kinetics,
 327 which provides the largest experimental data set for parameter fitting [26];
 328 and the Kortuz kinetics, which considers a recently discovered additional
 329 auto catalytic pathway [27]. Figure 7 shows the resulting Pareto fronts for
 330 an isothermal CSTR with the different kinetic models. The reactor propor-
 331 tions are adopted from the micro-Berty reactor reported by Vollbrecht and
 332 are summarized in Table 4 [28]. It can be observed that, although the
 333 steady state Pareto fronts differ considerably between the kinetic models,
 334 improvements through FPO compared to steady state operation are possi-
 335 ble in all four cases. In each case, the improvement is small at low yields
 336 and increases gradually along the Pareto front. For the Kortuz and Vanden
 337 Bussche kinetics, the improvement is most pronounced. The corresponding
 338 Pareto fronts exhibit a similar qualitative shape, with the Vanden Bussche
 339 model allowing a wider range toward high yields at very low product flow
 340 rates. For the Nestler and Brilman kinetics, the distance between the steady
 341 state and FPO fronts is smaller, indicating a lower improvement potential.
 342 The reason for this behavior can be clearly explained by the distance from
 343 chemical equilibrium. In the Brilman case, the reactor already operates very
 344 close to equilibrium under steady state conditions, resulting in only a minor
 345 improvement through FPO. The Nestler kinetics represent an intermediate
 346 distance from equilibrium, while the Kortuz and Vanden Bussche kinetics are

Figure 7: Comparison of Pareto fronts in the CSTR obtained with different kinetic models and the linearized reaction rate. a) Kortuz kinetics [27] b) van Schagen kinetics [26] c) Nestler kinetics [25] d) Vanden Bussche kinetic [24]

347 furthest away from equilibrium and therefore exhibit the highest potential
 348 for improvement under FPO.

349 To investigate the influence of the residence time effect, reference points
 350 are required around which the reaction rates can be linearized. Based on the
 351 average compositions obtained under FPO, the corresponding non-optimal
 352 steady states were determined. Around these steady states, the reaction rate
 353 was linearized by a Taylor series expansion at each Pareto point:

$$\mathbf{r}^{SS}(\mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{y}^{SS}) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial \mathbf{y}} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^{SS}). \quad (40)$$

354 Using the linearized reaction rate, the system response was simulated with
 355 the optimized parameters obtained from the nonlinear systems. The corre-
 356 sponding points are also provide in Figure 7. An improvement achieved with
 357 the linearized reaction rate can now only be explained by the bilinearity of
 358 the CSTR equations, and thus the residence time effect. As can be seen in

359 Figure 7, the Pareto front obtained with the linearized reaction rate lies very
360 close to, but slightly above, that of the nonlinear rate. This indicates that
361 the improvement results entirely from the residence time effect, while the
362 nonlinearity of the reaction rate is even counterproductive. This counter-
363 productive effect can be directly attributed to the chemical equilibrium term
364 present in the nonlinear rate expression. It limits the maximum achievable
365 yield for a given composition during the “batch” phase to the equilibrium
366 yield. In contrast, this limitation is absent in the linearized rate expression,
367 where the maximum possible yield is 100%.

368 It should be noted that the linear Pareto fronts were simulated using the
369 optimized operating conditions obtained from the full model, but were not
370 optimized themselves. The shape of both the steady state and FPO fronts
371 naturally depends on the nonlinearity of the reaction rate, as do the optimal
372 parameters. The periodic solution in this case is much more complex than the
373 three-phase behavior described in Section 2. Nevertheless, the improvement
374 can be attributed to the residence time effect and not to the nonlinearity of
375 the reaction rate.

376 For completeness, additional results as well as the optimal parameters
377 along the Pareto fronts for each case are provided in the Supporting Infor-
378 mation. Furthermore, the full set of model equations and the corresponding
379 optimization problems are presented there. All calculations in this work were
380 performed using the Julia programming language [29] and the JuMP opti-
381 mization framework [30], with Ipopt employed as the nonlinear solver [31].
382 The code used to generate the results presented in this paper is available on
383 GitHub¹.

384 4. Conclusion

385 This paper addresses the fundamental reason why forced periodic operation
386 with simultaneous modulation of inlet concentration and flow rate with
387 phase shift can provide performance improvements in chemical reactors. The
388 concept was first demonstrated using a simple $A \rightarrow C$ reaction, showing that
389 the bilinearity of the reactor model plays the major role in the improvement
390 potential. This bilinearity arises from the molar flow rate being used as an
391 input variable. From a physical perspective, this can be described as follows:

¹https://github.com/Jo1931/Paper_Leipold_FPO_Linear_2026

392 when the reactant concentration is high, the optimal phase shift is chosen
393 such that the residence time is maximized, and vice versa. In the limiting
394 case, the operation approaches a cyclic batch mode. Using methanol syn-
395 thesis as a case study, it was shown that the same principle also applies to
396 a realistic industrial process. Although the optimal temporal profiles differ
397 from those predicted for the simple $A \rightarrow C$ reaction, the improvement still
398 originates from the "residence time effect".

399 With the understanding that the improvement mainly originates from the
400 "residence time effect", FPO may also offer performance benefits for other
401 chemical reactions, provided that the system's nonlinearities do not impose
402 strong limitations. Suitable reactions should be operated sufficiently far from
403 chemical equilibrium and, most importantly, remain stable under periodic
404 forcing, which requires a robust catalyst. A possible example could be the
405 liquid-phase reaction of acetic anhydride, which has also been investigated
406 experimentally [11]. The findings of this work emphasize that FPO represents
407 a concept positioned between batch and continuous reactor operation and
408 may thus be beneficial for a wide range of chemical processes.

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413 **Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the** 414 **writing process**

415 The authors declare that the GPT-5.2 language model (ChatGPT, Ope-
416 nAI) was used during the writing and language editing process to improve
417 the clarity and readability of the manuscript. The authors reviewed and
418 verified all content to ensure accuracy and scientific integrity.

419 Nomenclature

Symbol [Unit]	Description
A, B, C	Components of the model reaction $A \rightarrow C$.
A_A, A_B, A_n	Amplitudes of periodic excitation for concentration and flow rate.
d [m]	Reactor diameter.
$f(x, u)$	Reactor model equations.
k [s ⁻¹]	Reaction rate constant.
l [m]	Reactor length.
m_{cat} [kg]	Catalyst mass.
n [mol]	Total number of moles.
n^G [mol]	Total number of moles in the gas phase.
\dot{n} [mol s ⁻¹]	Molar flow rate.
p [bar]	Reactor pressure.
r [mol s ⁻¹]	Reaction rate of the model reaction $A \rightarrow C$.
r_j [mol s ⁻¹ mol _{cat} ⁻¹]	Reaction rate of methanol synthesis reaction j .
$\text{squ}(\omega t)$	Square-wave excitation function.
T [K]	Reactor temperature.
u	Input vector of the reactor model.
x	State vector of the reactor model.
Y	Yield.
y	Mole fraction.
$\nu_{i,j}$	Stoichiometric coefficient of component i in reaction j .
ε	Constraint value in the ε -constraint method.
Φ_1 [mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹]	Average product flow rate.
Φ_2 [%]	Average yield.
φ [rad]	Phase shift between modulated inputs.
ω [rad s ⁻¹]	Angular frequency of periodic excitation.
τ [s]	Period duration of periodic operation.
Indices	
in	Inlet value.
out	Outlet value.
tot	Total value.
i	Component index.
j	Reaction index.

421

Abbreviations

CSTR	Continuous stirred tank reactor.
FBR	Fixed-bed reactor.
FPO	Forced periodic operation.
NFR	Nonlinear frequency response.
ODE	Ordinary differential equation.
PDE	Partial differential equation.
PFTR	Plug flow tubular reactor.
RWGS	Reverse water gas shift reaction.
SS	Steady state.
WGS	Water gas shift reaction.

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